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Marine Renewable Energy Adoption and Utility Ownership

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Abstract

Electric utilities in the United States, including private-owned utilities (i.e., investor owned utilities) and public-owned utilities (i.e., municipal utilities and electric cooperatives) offer different structures and approaches to generating, transmitting, and distributing energy. As the U.S. transitions toward a decarbonized grid, electric utilities remain key actors in the energy transition. Depending on a utility's ownership structure, there are enabling factors and barriers that affect the successful adoption of renewable energy technologies. This paper will compare utility ownership structures to understand the relationship between utility ownership and renewable energy adoption. The paper aims to identify which utility ownership structures are most conducive to marine renewable energy (MRE) adoption while elucidating how a given ownership structure facilitates scalable MRE development, demonstration, and deployment. The paper offers scenarios from Washington and Florida as examples to understand where and how MRE can grow within the U.S. given a specific utility ownership model.

Keywords: marine renewable energy; utility ownership, renewable energy adoption

1. Introduction

While all electric distribution utilities in the United States are tasked with powering communities across the country, how these utilities go about doing so varies along with their ownership structure. This variance in ownership structure produces different approaches by which these utilities procure and provide electricity to customers. Thus, as the U.S. moves toward decarbonizing the electricity sector, utilities remain key actors in navigating the transition to renewable energy resources. In this paper, we review literature on how utility ownership structure affects renewable energy adoption from several perspectives, including infrastructure investment, policy approaches, and generation mix. We do so with the intention to expand on the available literature and understand which utility ownership structures are driving (and have the potential to drive) marine renewable energy (MRE) adoption in the U.S. Our study process involved evaluating where the greatest potential for MRE is in the U.S., selecting a state-based assessment to compare how different ownership structures treat and consider MRE through an analysis of selected utility Integrated Resource Plans (IRPs), and a deep dive into a specific utility model example. Our study findings provide critical insight for project developers in the MRE sector that are navigating where the ripest opportunities are in the U.S.

In 2017, there were approximately 812 electric cooperatives (co-ops) serving 20 million customers, 1,958 publicly owned utilities (including federal, state, and municipal utilities (munis)) serving 24 million customers, and 168 investor-owned utilities (IOUs) serving 110 million customers across the U.S. [1]. These utilities, while having

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different ownership structures, provide electricity distribution to customers within their service territories. Within the public-owned utilities, munis (and Public Utility Districts (PUDs)) are city or county owned, whereas co-ops are owned by their customers. These public-owned utilities share functional similarities including public ownership, local control, nonprofit operations, low-cost structure, and customer-focused models. Munis and co-ops are not regulated by state public utility commissions (PUCs) and are instead governed by elected or appointed boards, mayors, city council members, or citizens. Public-owned utilities collectively serve 28% of U.S. energy customers [1]. Typically, munis serve a single city/urban region, whereas co-ops can service large service territories but mostly small populations. Having local and independent control and regulation provides public-owned utility decisionmakers the opportunity for community engagement to understand and integrate their customers' needs and values in their decision-making [2].

On the other hand, IOUs are always regulated by a state utility commission and are shareholder-owned for-profit companies. IOUs often contain service territories that cross one or more states. While customers may have less influence or voice within the operation of IOUs, the PUCs regulate the utilities to ensure energy goals are being met (energy affordability, reliability, and security) in addition to ensuring fair practices in rates and customer protection. While numerically there are fewer IOUs that serve electricity customers than public-owned utilities, IOUs serve significantly more customers than co-ops and munis combined. In 2017, IOUs served 72% of electricity customers across the U.S [1]. As a result, IOUs are the largest electricity distributor due to the significant number of customers they serve.

1.1. Utility Ownership and Renewable Energy Adoption

The differences in ownership model and the resultant variations in governance and operational processes across private and public owned utilities often leads to variability in the openness and pace to adopt new energy technologies. Utilities can either facilitate or pose barriers in the progress toward adopting renewable energy. One way to assess this is through an examination of utility investment patterns. [3] studied this relationship in the European Union (EU) and determined that public electric utilities invest a larger share of their investment portfolio (33%) into renewables than their private counterparts (11%). This factor was determined to be especially apparent in EU countries with ambitious climate policies and regulatory environments. The impact of policy is further explored in [4] and [5], where the author showed how municipalities that own their electric utilities were more likely to adopt sustainable energy policies, including renewable energy promoting policies. Through a series of statistical analyses, the author found that municipalities that owned their utilities (i.e., munis) adopted more community-wide, sustainable energy policies than municipalities with IOUs. [6] corroborates these findings, concluding that U.S. municipalities with public-owned utilities adopt more clean energy policies than U.S. municipalities with IOUs.

Understanding the driving mechanisms behind policy adoption and approaches reveals further insight into how different utility ownership structures position themselves to renewable energy resources. [5] determined that municipal utilities' ability to build "fiscal capacity" synergizes with municipal governments' ability to build "technical capacity" in a hyper-localized context that facilitates their high rate of sustainable energy policy adoption. A municipally owned utility's fiscal capacity enables them to redistribute excess revenue to funding clean energy initiatives, whereas excess revenue would be profit for shareholders if the utility were an IOU.

Another means of assessing whether IOUs, munis, or co-ops are most amenable to adopting renewables is the composition of their generation portfolios. [7] and [8] determined that rural states and rural electric co-ops are more likely to generate electricity from renewables than IOUs or municipally owned utilities, concluding further study is necessary to understand the mechanism driving this observation. Across the U.S., private and public utilities collectively owned approximately 55% of the total renewable energy generating capacity in 2019 [9]. However, it is worth noting that public-owned utilities (be it munis or co-ops) generate a small fraction of the renewable energy power supply — eg. 21.7% generation supply by public utilities compared to 37.7% by IOUs and 40.6% by independent power producers [10].

1.2. Understanding Utility Ownership for MRE Adoption

Understanding how utility ownership models have historically affected general renewable energy adoption may provide insight regarding MRE adoption. Energy technologies at a nascent stage of development like MRE require an enabling environment to become commercially viable and readily deployable. MRE has a role to play in the goal to decarbonize the U.S. power sector by 2035. As such, it is vital to target the ripest locations (i.e., by resource potential, enabling policy environments, and interest from utility/developer partners) to ensure project success.

Almost 40% of the U.S. population lives in a community located along the coast with access to the ocean where energy can be generated using technologies such as tidal barrages and wave energy converters [11]. MRE is generated from waves, tides, and currents found in oceans, tidal areas, or estuaries. Across the U.S., total MRE potential is estimated to be 2,300 TWh/yr, which is almost 57% of the energy generation in the U.S. in 2019 [12]. As a result, implementing MRE technologies can significantly contribute to meeting the nation's energy needs. Additionally, using MRE could reduce carbon emissions by an estimated 500 million tons per year [13]. MRE, if used in tandem with desalination plants, MRE could also benefit coastal communities that have unreliable grid connections and critical infrastructure needs [14]. With increased federal and state incentives, MRE has the potential to be competitive with other renewable energy sources [15].

This study aims to understand the role utility ownership plays in the quest to achieve MRE adoption. In Section 2 the study methods are described; Section 3 provides the study results; and Section 4 offers a discussion and concludes paper.

2. Study Methodology

We aim to begin answering the following question: Which utilities and ownership structures are driving MRE adoption in the U.S. (including development and demonstration)? Our intent is to provide insight for MRE developers on how to navigate the landscape of varying utility ownership structures across the U.S. in regions where there is significant potential for MRE development. To understand the opportunity for MRE adoption among different utility ownership structures, we first defined what we mean by technology adoption. Technology adoption may be interpreted as a series of events that leads to the widespread proliferation of a given technology, spanning activities from research and development projects to large-scale technology investment.

To answer our research question, we developed a high-level approach to begin understanding the relationship between utility ownership structure and MRE adoption in the U.S. through state-based assessments. Our first step involved identifying regions with MRE resource development potential using a 2021 report on MRE development opportunities in the U.S. [12]. This report provides information on where the greatest potential is for MRE development in the U.S. using a measure known as “technical power potential” (TPP). The report suggests that the top four regions with the most TPP are Alaska, the East Coast, Hawaii, and the West Coast. From these regions, we chose Washington and Florida for our state-based assessment solely based on data availability to help with our analysis. For these two states, we relied on information in utility IRPs and other publicly available data to assess the differences in utility ownership structure and MRE adoption. At a very high level, IRPs outline a utility's plans and decision-making process for future resource generation mix, determining investment strategies for generation technology options. Through examining IRPs, we gleaned information on the utilities' practices and how they discuss and consider MRE by highlighting their posture toward MRE resource development [16]. [16] summarizes utility treatment and openness toward MRE along the following spectrum from lowest to highest consideration and actionability—the categories of interest include: MRE included in lists, MRE included in discussion with no analyses, MRE analyzed in a pre-screening setting, and MRE included in portfolio analysis. In our analysis, we first explore Washington State through the consideration and actionability factor categories, and then expand on those findings by analyzing a specific scenario in a Florida utility context.

3. Study Results

3.1. Washington

Washington State has a significant TPP for MRE, a renewable portfolio standard (RPS) that applies equally to all utility ownership structures, and a heterogeneous utility ownership mix of IOUs, munis, and co-ops. Washington is a leading state for developing MRE resources due to its unique geography along the Pacific Coast. With a TPP of 43 TWh per year, the state possesses some of the greatest potential for wave, tidal, and river energy in the contiguous U.S. [12]. The state's Energy Independence Act (referred to as EIA or I-937) established an RPS mandate that applies to all electric utilities serving a population of 25,000 customers or more, totaling 18 electric utilities altogether (the state has 61 utilities in total), which will be the focus of our analysis for this paper. Three of those 18 utilities are IOUs—Avista Corporation, PacifiCorp, and Puget Sound Energy (PSE)—while the rest are public utilities (munis and co-ops).

In our analysis, we found that seven electric utilities mention MRE in some capacity in their IRPs [16]. That list includes Avista, Orcas Power & Light Co-Op (OPALCO), PacifiCorp, PSE, Seattle City Light, Snohomish County PUD, and Tacoma Power. While all three of Washington's IOUs make the list of electric utilities considering MRE

in their IRPs in some capacity, Avista and PSE go no further than including MRE in general lists or discussion with no analysis (this category also includes Seattle City Light and Tacoma Power). These utilities depict MRE resources as being commercially unfeasible with a lack of referenceable demonstration. PSE specifically states that MRE technology immaturity is its reason for excluding MRE from further analysis and consideration.

PacifiCorp goes a step further than its Washington State IOU counterparts in its position toward MRE adoption by analyzing MRE in a pre-screening setting. The pre-screening process includes performing a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) assessment and determining capital costs, which highlights the second category of utilities that demonstrated an increased level of consideration and treatment toward MRE (compared to IRPs that include MRE in lists or discussion only with no analysis). Although utilities that use pre-screening go a step further than the first category, pre-screening analysis is often used to deselect unfeasible generation resources from a longer list of generation options to be considered in the phase of portfolio analyses. Therefore, our study found that utilities that analyze MRE in only a pre-screening setting exclude MRE as a potential generation resource due to possible limitations in LCOE and capital cost assessments. It is worth noting that Tacoma Power, a municipally owned utility falling into the previous category for its consideration of MRE in its IRP, researched the possibility of developing a tidal stream generation asset in 2007 independent of their IRP [17]. The utility conducted a separate feasibility study that produced an LCOE for a potential tidal energy installation.

Another Washington utility that joins PacifiCorp in the pre-screening analysis category is the co-op OPALCO. OPALCO is unique in that its pre-screening analysis of LCOE and capital costs is intended to determine when MRE resources may have “grid parity” [18]. OPALCO defines grid parity to mean a future scenario where MRE resources become cost competitive with existing onshore resources. OPALCO substituted this grid parity analysis for a portfolio-level analysis. This grid parity analysis beyond a pre-screening analysis indicates a level of treatment and consideration for MRE adoption that falls in between the pre-screening and portfolio analysis categories.

Snohomish County PUD is the only Washington utility that evaluated MRE resources in a portfolio analysis, the highest level of treatment and consideration for MRE adoption. Snohomish County PUD, which is a municipally owned utility, considered tidal energy in their 2010 IRP’s preferred resource portfolio and made great strides toward developing MRE generation assets over a seven-year period. Snohomish County PUD boasts being a “national leader in the research and development of tidal energy,” having received the first Federal Energy Regulatory Commission license for a deep-water tidal energy array [19]. The Snohomish County PUD engaged local, state, and federal agencies, MRE industry partners, environmental NGOs, and national labs and developed and published a series of studies, such as mitigation and monitoring plans for its pilot Admiralty Inlet tidal power plant that produced invaluable baseline knowledge for the MRE sector. Although the utility was unsuccessful due to costs and funding challenges, ultimately cancelling their pilot MRE project in 2014, their efforts set a noteworthy precedent for what municipally owned utilities can achieve in MRE adoption.

3.2. Florida

After identifying public-owned utilities (specifically munis) as more conducive for MRE adoption in our WA assessment, we extended the work to focus on a single muni in Florida to explore the contributing factors. Florida possesses immense ocean current, wave, and tidal energy resources due to its extensive coastline and proximity to the Gulf Stream [12]. Four of the top five tidal power sites in the Gulf Coast region belong to Florida. Florida also houses the Southeast National Marine Renewable Energy Center (SNMREC) at Florida Atlantic University. The U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) established SNMREC as one of three research centers in the U.S. dedicated to assisting industry with the development of MRE resources [20].

Altogether, there are 58 electric utilities serving the state: 5 IOUs, 35 municipal utilities, and 18 co-ops [21]. However, one utility stood out for exploration in this study: City of Lake Worth Beach Electric Utility (LWBEU). When discussing the role of electric utilities in Florida’s development of MRE resources, LWBEU was found to be a critical partner in both exploring and supporting paths to commercially feasible, utility-scale MRE despite their limited capacity to leverage economies of scale compared to IOUs. DOE awarded 1 million dollars to SNMREC in partnership with LWBEU to further explore MRE technology capabilities off the city’s coast [22]. SNMREC envisions MRE development projects like these growing 100 times in scale to create an unprecedented MRE R&D site connected to the City of Lake Worth Beach’s electric grid [20]. LWBEU took several steps to create a landscape conducive to justifying, exploring, demonstrating, and developing MRE resources, some activities of which were captured in their 2019 Annual Report [23].

LWBEU organized and funded an MRE community economic impact study for their service area. Their goal was to understand how being an early participant in MRE development would affect community economic development. From this study, the utility learned that investing in MRE development would have a multiplying

effect on local economic development with recurring benefits for years to come. LWBEU also hired an offshore engineering firm to conduct a scoping study to understand the technical feasibility and potential options for offshore MRE infrastructure development. The study considered where infrastructure such as cables would be routed, technical specifications such as cable length, and where infrastructure would be sited along the shore. This study also included considerations for what the real-world costs would be for developing this infrastructure and establishing an offshore industrial technology park to support MRE development. Separately, LWBEU is taking proactive measures to harden existing electricity infrastructure, establishing a capacity that futureproofs infrastructure to support MRE technology integration into the municipality's electric grid [24]. In 2021, LWBEU worked with the city to approve \$44 million in electricity infrastructure improvements [25]. All these actions taken by the utility were to achieve a preparedness level conducive to MRE resource development and adoption.

LWBEU's motivation behind their partnership with SNMREC and their actions to support MRE resource development are rooted in their commitment to community benefit and their prioritization of socioecological resilience. This is captured in LWBEU's amenability to assume more risk for less-developed renewable energy generation projects if the technology can be demonstrated and economically justified. Public-owned utilities tend to have a bottom-up strategy, driven philosophically by placing utility customer/community members first, as opposed to shareholders. This is demonstrated by LWBEU's commitment to all major decisions for asset generation and distribution being governed by an elected body.

4. Discussion of Results and Conclusion

The results section yields critical insight into the research question regarding which utility ownership structures are driving MRE adoption in the U.S. One key finding in the context of Washington State is that public-owned utilities are considering MRE more seriously than their private-owned utilities. Compared to IOUs Avista, PSE, and PacifiCorp, OPALCO and Snohomish County PUD's posture toward MRE resources in their IRPs reflects a commitment to treating MRE as a potential generation option alongside other resources. Even though OPALCO and Snohomish serve far fewer customers in smaller service areas and are less able to leverage economies of scale, both public-owned utilities employed MRE assessment and adoption promoting measures that surpass Washington's IOUs. Snohomish County PUD goes so far as to be a national leader in the MRE sector, making critical sector contributions and pilot advancements despite its limited capital and operation resources. Their approach to MRE aligns with findings from the literature review that demonstrate munis as being key actors in driving the national renewable energy transition [26]. Snohomish County PUD leveraged a multiscale, multifaceted approach to support MRE development, similar to LWBEU, another muni based in Florida driving MRE adoption in an entirely different region than Washington State.

The actions of Snohomish County PUD and LWBEU highlight that munis tend to have comparatively stronger appetite for MRE resources. Despite Florida having no state RPS, LWBEU remains ardent in supporting the development and demonstration of MRE resources. LWBEU invested in studying the socioeconomic, technical, and environmental aspects of MRE, grounding their exploration into MRE on the basis of community benefits and economic development. The City of Lake Worth Beach and LWBEU are prime examples of a municipal government and its utility synergizing to simultaneously build technical and fiscal capacity in a hyper-localized context to drive MRE adoption [4]. LWBEU's motivations and explanation behind its MRE-promoting actions align with findings about public-owned utilities actions being anchored in community engagement and learning strategies [27]. The muni invested in research targeted at understanding and translating what MRE resources mean for the local communities it serves.

LWBEU and Snohomish County PUD actions taken together also support existing literature stating that munis intend to lead the renewable energy transition by redefining their roles as distribution utilities [27]. Both utilities are implementing strategies that welcome new energy generation technology configurations including setting MRE R&D precedents and forging new institutional relationships that build MRE readiness capacity. Additionally, these results complement growing public sentiments and empirical evidence that U.S. IOUs are currently laggards in the clean energy transition [8]. Further research could explore additional lessons learned in how munis in other U.S. states/regions with an appetite for MRE can expand efforts for adoption.

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